
MODELS OF TEACHER LEARNING

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Annotation: The article covers important information about models of teacher learning in modern education system. On the other hand, significant points about models of teaching and learning were discussed.

Key words: *teachers-in-service, Applied Science Model, research-based theories, practical level, “scientific” solution, The Craft Model, student-centered approaches.*

The current educational climate is essentially driven by an overriding interest in preparing students to become effective teachers. Therefore, some teacher education programmes have been developed in order to enhance this process. These programmes explore the possible approaches which could encourage student-teachers or teachers-in-service towards learning-focused teaching activities. Although teacher education programmes have been in existence for a long time, ESL teacher education is a relatively recent development. Numerous educational theorists and practitioners have handed down different opinions on the possible models for teacher education from their personal point of views. However, most of the researchers shared three common views. Subsequently these three concepts attained worldwide critical acclamation as teaching models. The latest models of teacher education have been put forward by, Michael J. Wallace in 1991. Wallace moulded his models after the existing concepts of his precursors, but in a more convenient or transparent way[1].

1. The Applied Science Model is the traditional and perhaps still the most prevalent model underlying most ESL teacher education programmes. It was

put forward by Michael J. Wallace in 1991 based on the Technical Rationality of Donald A. Schön. The model derives its authority from the achievements of empirical science, particularly in the 19th and the 20th centuries. The Applied Science Model emerges on the following assumptions:

- Teaching is a science and as such can be examined rationally and objectively.
- Teachers learn to be teachers by being taught research-based theories.
- These theories are being conveyed to the students only by those who are considered to be the experts in the particular field.
- Teachers are said to be educated when they become proficient enough to apply these theories in practice.

Merits: The Applied Science Model has the following plus points: This model takes into account the crucial element of the explosive growth of relevant scientific knowledge in recent times. Its theory oriented study provides much opportunity for the learner to achieve received knowledge. Demerits: In spite of its wide-spread usage, it has some shortcomings:

- Changes at the practical level applied by practitioners are not taken into account; therefore, their value is underestimated, thereby creating a separation between research and professional practice.
- The most serious problem occurs when the students are asked to apply on their own the scientific theories they have learned in classroom.
- Another shortcoming is the Applied Science Model's failure to address adequately many of the important issues in teaching English. There has been relatively little research that directly concerns the teaching and learning of English in the classroom.
- Many researchers claim that trainees who take courses based on the Applied Science Model feel that such courses do not help them develop professionally, that is, the theoretical studies are of no help.

Here the learner is passive, he cannot ask any question. He just follows the instructions of the expert. The Applied Science Model is somewhat limited in scope as it does not take care of student- teachers' self-development or awareness of their role not only as teachers but as teacher-researchers in their classrooms. In Applied Science Model teaching is based on external knowledge, because it is essentially depended on rules and principles derived from preexisting knowledge sources. The Applied Science Model is prescriptive since it advocates teachers to follow some proven teaching method instead of relying upon individual or intuitive theories of teaching and learning. The Applied Science Model is a product oriented model. It slavishly follows various established methods and theories to improve teaching ability. In this model there is no scope for expressing one's creativity. Its major shortcoming is that it has not been able to deliver a relevant "scientific" solution to the various professional dilemmas that the teacher faces in real-life classroom situations.

2. The Craft Model is the oldest form of professional education and is still used today in ESL teacher education, albeit rather limitedly. Its conceptual basis, however, is widely utilized in practicum courses in which students work with classroom teachers, often called cooperating teachers. Its use in one course in a programme of ESL teacher education cannot be regarded as a model for an entire programme. The basic assumptions underlying this model are as follows:

- ✓ In its most basic form, Craft Model consists of the trainee or beginner working closely with the expert teacher.
- ✓ The practitioner is supposed to learn by imitating all the teaching techniques used by the experienced teacher.
- ✓ Knowledge is acquired as a result of observation, instruction, and practice.

Merits: The positive sides of this model are as follows: The Craft Model of second language teacher education allows the learner to

develop experiential knowledge, since the primary responsibilities of the learner are in the classroom. It is one of the quickest models of ESL teacher education. Researches proved that students can imitate their teacher very quickly. Demerits: This model of ESL teacher education programme suffers from several shortcomings:

- ✓ The most relevant strategies of training are provided by experts, thus the student-teachers play a passive role.
- ✓ The Craft Model is essentially conservative. It does not account for any kind of change. It depends merely on imitation.
- ✓ It does not handle the relevant scientific knowledge.
- ✓ In this model there is no scope for developing one's creativity since it does not allow suggesting new theories.

3. The reflective practice has become a dominant paradigm in language teacher education research and programmes worldwide. But it is not an innovation in teaching. It has its roots in the work of a number of educational theorists and practitioners. Most definitions on reflective thinking found in the literature of teacher education are based on Dewey's inquiry oriented concepts. In the 1980s, Dewey's foundational aspects on reflection were further extended by the American sociologist Donald A. Schön. Later on, in 1991 Michael J. Wallace described Schön's critique in a more explicit way. The Reflective Model is based on the assumption that teachers develop professional competence through reflecting on their own practice. In other words, a teaching experience is recalled and considered to reach an evaluation and to provide input into future planning and action.

Teachers can enhance learning by using different teaching styles. Traditional lectures and student-centered approaches are two models. Each has pros and cons. It's important for teachers to choose the right mix for effective education in today's changing landscape. Using different teaching styles is important for a few reasons[2]. It helps students learn in ways that suit them, allows teachers to adapt to student needs and the curriculum, promotes critical thinking and collaboration

skills, and keeps the classroom interesting. Overall, it makes learning better for students and teaching more effective and enjoyable for everyone.

It should be noted that if you are a practicing educator at any level, you may not yet realize this, but you need not reinvent the wheel when you are looking for effective ways to teach. There are literally hundreds of models of teaching and learning. To reiterate, simply put models deal with the ways in which learning environments and instructional experiences can be constructed, sequenced, or delivered. They may provide theoretical or instructional frameworks, patterns, or examples for any number of educational components — curricula, teaching techniques, instructional groupings, classroom management plans, content development, sequencing, delivery, the development of support materials, presentation methods, etc. Teaching models may even be discipline or student-population specific[3].

Models of teaching and learning are critical pieces to instructional planning and delivery because they help educators:

- 1) develop highly tuned and more varied professional repertoires;
- 2) allow them to reach larger numbers of students more effectively;
- 3) create either more uniform, or varied, or effective instructional events, guided by targeted subjects, content, or processes;
- 4) understand curricular foci better, especially as different models can be matched specifically to both learning outcomes and/or targeted learning populations;
- 5) gain needed insights into why some methods work with some learners, while others do not;
- 6) radically modify or redesign existing methods of teaching and instructional delivery so that emerging or altered instructional techniques may better meet the needs of today's students.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that there are many teaching methods that modern educators must choose from. Modeling in teaching is among the most popular methods many of us are familiar with.

Modeling in teaching is a technique instructors use every day, sometimes even without being consciously aware of it. A music teacher who doesn't play an instrument wouldn't attempt to teach it to a class. It's important that the instructor always has an appropriate mastery over a skill before they attempt to teach it to others. However, by taking control of the process, teachers will have greater efficacy. Modeling in teaching is an instructional strategy. It makes clear the topic that's being taught at the beginning of a lesson, thereby helping to reduce the number of errors in a student's work. The teacher models a concept and then explains it to the class. It's an effective means of creating a road map for learning. One of the biggest benefits of modeling in teaching is how widely it can be used. It can be applied in any subject, with all kinds of learners, including those with special needs.

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